

Studies on the Chelation of 3-Hydroxynaphthalene-2-Carboxylic Acid with Zinc(II), Cadmium(II) and Uranyl(II)

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The stability constants of the complexes of 3-hydroxynaphthalene-2-carboxylic acid with Zn(II), Cd(II) and UO₂(II) have been obtained potentiometrically in 50 vol % dioxane-water medium at three temperatures and ionic strength 0.1M (KNO₃) following the Bjerrum-Calvin technique as applied by Irving and Rossotti. The values of overall changes in ΔG , ΔH and ΔS have been evaluated.

The thermodynamic stability constants have also been reported by determining the stability constants of the complexes at 30° and four different ionic strengths and then extrapolating to zero ionic strength.

THE capacity of 3-hydroxynaphthalene-2-carboxylic acid to act as an efficient complexing agent for different metal ions has been studied by various workers under different experimental conditions.^{1,2} The stability constants, thermodynamic functions and thermodynamic stability constants of Y(III), Ce(III), La(III), Pr(III), Nd(III), Gd(III), Dy(III), Er(III), Yb(III), Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) complexes with the above ligand in aqueous dioxane (50%, v/v) at three temperatures and four different ionic strengths have already been reported in our earlier communications³.

In the present study, the stability constants, thermodynamic functions of Zn(II), Cd(II) and UO₂(II) complexes with 3-hydroxynaphthalene-2-carboxylic acid have been determined in aqueous dioxane (50%, v/v) at 20°, 30° and 40° at 0.1M (KNO₃) ionic strength following Irving-Rossotti titration technique⁴. Thermodynamic stability constants have also been reported by determining the stability constants of the complexes at 30° and four ionic strengths of 0.05M, 0.10M, 0.15M, 0.20M (KNO₃) and then extrapolating to zero ionic strength. Attempts to study complexation with Hg(II) resulted in failure because of its precipitation at a very low pH.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The double distilled CO₂ free water was used in all experimental work. Dioxane was purified by the recommended procedure⁵. Metal nitrate solutions were prepared by dissolving the corresponding metal salts in double distilled water and standardized by standard volumetric methods. The ligand solution (0.05M) was prepared by dissolving in dioxane. The mole ratio of metal to ligand was kept 1 : 5 in order to fulfil the maximum coordination number of the metal ion.

Photovolt digital pH meter type M-120 (U.S.A.) calibrated by suitable buffers before use and having

an accuracy of ± 0.002 units was used to follow the change in pH during the titrations which were carried out in a cell immersed in a thermostated bath maintained at 20° \pm 0.1°, 30° \pm 0.1° and 40° \pm 0.1°. The design of the cell was such that it could accommodate a glass stirrer, a micro burette and a glass electrode.

The three solutions (total volume 50 ml in each case) were prepared as follows :

A, 1.0 \times 10⁻² M HNO₃ ; B, 1.0 \times 10⁻² M HNO₃ + 5.0 \times 10⁻² M ligand ; C, 1.0 \times 10⁻² M HNO₃ + 5.0 \times 10⁻² M ligand + 1.0 \times 10⁻² M metal ion solution. such that the concentrations of the common ingredients were identical in different cases. An appropriate quantity of potassium nitrate solution (1.0M) was added to maintain the desired ionic strength. The above solutions were titrated against standard potassium hydroxide solution prepared in aqueous dioxane (50%, v/v).

The concentrations were corrected for the changes in volume produced by the addition of alkali during titrations. The difference in the amount of potassium hydroxide utilised for the last two titrations (B and C) is a measure of extent of complexation. From the titration curves it is observed that the metal ligand curve is well separated from the ligand titration curve proving that the liberation of protons is due to chelation.

Results and Discussion

Values of formation functions \bar{n}_A , \bar{n} and pL were calculated using the standard expressions⁴.

The calculations of practical stability constants of proton complexes were done by plotting \bar{n}_A versus pH and then applying various computational methods^{6,7}. The mean values of protonation constants of the

TABLE 1—VALUES OF PROTONATION CONSTANTS, STABILITY CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS AT THREE TEMPERATURES.

Cation	Constants	Method	Temperature			-ΔG (Kcalmole ⁻¹)			ΔH (Kcal mole ⁻¹) at 30°	ΔS (cal mole ⁻¹ degree ⁻¹) at 30°
			20°	30°	40°	20°	30°	40°		
H(I)	log ^P K ₁ ^H		11.52	11.25	10.95					
	log ^P K ₂ ^H		2.78	2.65	2.45					
	log ^P β ₂ ^H		14.30	13.90	13.40					
Zn(II)	log K ₁	(i)	8.69	8.55	8.35					
		(ii)	8.69	8.55	8.35					
		(iii)	8.55	8.47	8.31					
		(iv)	8.28	8.26	7.98					
log K ₂	(i)	8.42	8.05	8.00						
	(ii)	8.42	—	8.00						
	(iii)	8.43	—	7.97						
	(iv)	8.84	8.34	8.37						
Cd(II)	log β ₂	(i)	17.12	16.60	16.35	22.96	23.01	23.41	-16.2	+22.4
		(ii)	7.92	7.60	7.43					
		(iii)	7.92	7.60	7.43					
		(iv)	7.92	7.56	7.33					
log K ₂	(i)	7.50	7.21	7.04						
	(ii)	7.65	7.28	7.11						
	(iii)	7.65	7.28	7.11						
	(iv)	7.64	7.22	7.13						
UO ₂ (II)	log β ₂	(i)	15.57	14.88	14.54	20.88	20.62	20.82	-21.4	-2.6
		(ii)	11.04	10.04	10.06					
		(iii)	—	—	—					
		(iv)	10.97	9.88	10.01					
log K ₂	(i)	9.78	9.20	8.70						
	(ii)	9.78	9.20	8.70						
	(iii)	9.77	9.20	8.60						
	(iv)	9.85	9.36	8.75						
log β ₂	(i)	20.82	19.24	18.76	27.92	26.67	26.86	-42.8	-53.4	
	(ii)	—	—	—						
	(iii)	—	—	—						
	(iv)	—	—	—						

(i) Bjerrum's half integral method ; (ii) Graphical method ;
 (iii) Interpolation at various n values ; (iv) Method of successive approximations.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF THE PROTONATION CONSTANTS OF THE LIGAND AND CONCENTRATION STABILITY CONSTANTS OF COMPLEXES AT 30°

Cation	Constants	Method	μ=0.05M	μ=0.10M	μ=0.15M	μ=0.20M
H(I)	log ^P K ₁ ^H		11.30	11.25	11.20	11.15
	log ^P K ₂ ^H		2.70	2.65	2.60	2.55
	log ^P β ₂ ^H		14.00	13.90	13.80	13.70
Zn(II)	log K ₁	(i)	8.75	8.55	8.46	8.25
		(ii)	8.75	8.55	8.46	8.25
		(iii)	8.81	8.47	8.44	8.24
		(iv)	8.42	8.26	8.11	8.01
log K ₂	(i)	8.35	8.05	8.08	7.63	
	(ii)	—	—	8.08	—	
	(iii)	—	—	8.07	—	
	(iv)	8.69	8.34	8.43	7.87	
Cd(II)	log β ₂	(i)	17.11	16.60	16.54	15.88
		(ii)	7.98	7.60	7.55	7.25
		(iii)	7.98	7.60	7.55	7.25
		(iv)	7.96	7.56	7.57	7.27
log K ₂	(i)	7.68	7.21	7.15	6.98	
	(ii)	7.52	7.28	7.25	6.71	
	(iii)	—	7.28	—	—	
	(iv)	—	7.22	—	—	
UO ₂ (II)	log β ₂	(i)	7.83	7.67	7.65	6.98
		(ii)	15.51	14.88	14.80	13.96
		(iii)	10.12	10.04	10.00	9.90
		(iv)	—	—	—	—
log K ₂	(i)	—	—	—	—	
	(ii)	—	—	—	—	
	(iii)	—	—	—	—	
	(iv)	9.96	9.88	9.92	9.80	
log β ₂	(i)	9.30	9.20	8.80	8.86	
	(ii)	9.30	9.20	8.80	8.86	
	(iii)	9.33	9.20	8.72	8.82	
	(iv)	9.46	9.36	8.88	8.97	
log β ₂	(i)	19.42	19.24	18.80	18.77	
	(ii)	—	—	—	—	
	(iii)	—	—	—	—	
	(iv)	—	—	—	—	

(i) Bjerrum's half integral method ; (ii) Graphical method ;
 (iii) Interpolation at various n values ; (iv) Method of successive approximations.

ligand at three temperatures, one ionic strength and four ionic strengths, one temperature have been summarized in Table 1 and Table 2 respectively.

The metal-ligand stability constants have been obtained by analysis of the formation curves obtained by plotting \bar{n} versus pL . These plots indicate that the values of \bar{n} obtained are of the order of two for all the metal ions under study, indicating the formation of both 1:1 and 1:2 complexes. Bjerrum's half integral method⁶, interpolation at various \bar{n} values, graphical method⁷ and extended to dioxane-water mixture by Van Uitert and Haas⁸ were used to calculate $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$. In certain cases where there were very few values of \bar{n} below or above one, the value of $\log K_1$ or $\log K_2$ was obtained by interpolation at mid point using the following relationship

$$\log K_1 K_2 = 2 pL \text{ (at } \bar{n} = 1 \text{)}$$

Both the method of interpolation at various \bar{n} values and graphical method were inapplicable in these cases. Since the ratio of successive constants was less than 10^4 , the method of successive approximations⁷ was used to refine the values of stability constants obtained by Bjerrum's half integral method. The values of stepwise stability constants obtained by various methods and of overall stability constants obtained by the method of successive approximations have been reported. The error limits are ± 0.05 for $\log K$ values.

The small difference between successive constants suggests that the formation of two types of complexes ML_1 and ML_2 proceed simultaneously and may be attributed to the smaller steric hindrance offered by 3-hydroxynaphthalene-2-carboxylic acid as compared with coordinated water molecule.

The data show a decrease in the values of overall protonation constants and stability constants with increase of temperature. The values of overall changes in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) accompanying complexation have been determined using the temperature coefficient and Gibbs Helmholtz equation⁹, using the refined values of stability constants (Table 1). The precision of ΔG , ΔH and ΔS values are ± 0.08 Kcal mole⁻¹, ± 0.1 Kcal mole⁻¹ and ± 0.3 cal degree⁻¹ mole⁻¹ respectively.

ΔG values for Zn^{2+} complex are more negative with increase of temperature showing that complex formation is a spontaneous process. Whereas for Cd^{2+} , UO_2^{2+} complexes no such regular order is observed. The enthalpy change (ΔH) being negative in all cases is favourable for the formation of these complexes. The entropy change (ΔS) being positive in case of Zn^{2+} complex is favourable but for Cd^{2+} and UO_2^{2+} complexes, ΔS° being negative does not favour the formation of these complexes.

The metal-ligand stability data at various μ values (Table 2) reveal that $\log \beta_2$ values decrease with an

increase in the ionic strength of the medium. According to Hückel¹⁰, the activity of the metal ion for its interaction with other molecular species varies in inverse proportion to ionic strength of the medium. On this basis, the decrease in stability for 3-hydroxynaphthalene-2-carboxylic acid complexes with the metal ions under study in solution of increasing ionic strength is justified.

The values of log step stability constants at various ionic strengths, extrapolated to zero ionic strength gave step thermodynamic stability constant¹¹. These values are shown in Table 3 as $\log K_1^{\mu=0}$ and $\log K_2^{\mu=0}$. Their sum is shown as calculated $\log K^{\mu=0}$. The values of overall stability constants $\log \beta_2$ at various ionic strengths were likewise extrapolated to zero ionic strength and the overall thermodynamic stability constants thus obtained have been symbolised as experimental $\log K^{\mu=0}$.

TABLE 3.—VALUES OF THERMODYNAMIC STABILITY CONSTANTS AND FREE ENERGIES AT 30°.

	Metal ions		
	Zn(II)	Cd(II)	UO ₂ (II)
$\log K_1^{\mu=0}$	8.56	7.91	10.01
$\log K_2^{\mu=0}$	8.96	8.11	9.62
Calcd $\log K^{\mu=0}$	17.52	16.02	19.63
Exptl $\log K^{\mu=0}$	17.52	16.02	19.63
ΔF_1 (Kcal mole ⁻¹)	-11.86	-10.96	-13.87
ΔF_2 (Kcal mole ⁻¹)	-12.42	-11.24	-13.33
Calcd ΔF (Kcal mole ⁻¹)	-24.28	-22.20	-27.20
Exptl ΔF (Kcal mole ⁻¹)	-24.28	-22.20	-27.20

Ligational standard free energy change was obtained from the expression

$$\Delta F = -2.303RT \log K^{\mu=0}$$

The precision of ΔF value is ± 0.08 Kcal mole⁻¹.

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